

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF FUNDS IN THE FIELD OF LABOR PROTECTION

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ANNOTATION: In this article, funds in the field of labor protection, the use and direction of funds are analytically studied, and the role of these funds in the economy of the enterprise, region and republic is analyzed.

KEY WORDS: “Labor protection, economy. Accident, the law, the employer, employee trade union”.

INTRODUCTION. Article 16 of the Labor Protection Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan is called Labor Protection Financing. The sources of financing of the funds and the rules for their use are defined. It is used to prevent various accidents and occupational diseases and prevent losses in labor relations.

RESEARCH METHODS. Methods such as analysis of scientific and educational literature, comparative analysis, generalization, programming and digitization models were used in the research process.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS OBTAINED. Financing of labor protection is carried out at the expense of: Budget funds allocated from the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan; employer's own funds; Funds of labor protection funds established in accordance with the law; sponsorship donations of legal entities and individuals; other sources not prohibited by law.

Budgetary funds for labor protection are allocated in the relevant (republican and local) budgets with a separate note, from these funds are used for the provision of management bodies, supervisory and inspection bodies, financing of research and development works, state programs related to labor protection and other used to execute programs.

Each employer allocates funds necessary for labor protection in the amount determined by legislation, a collective agreement, as well as collective agreements or other internal regulatory documents. Employees do not make any expenses for these purposes.

Organizations have the right to establish a labor protection fund at the expense of profits (revenues) from their commercial activities and other activities, as well as other sources not

prohibited by law.

Funds intended for labor protection cannot be used for other purposes.

The procedure for allocation of funds by the employer for labor protection, as well as the establishment of funds for labor protection and the use of their funds is determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the participation of the Federation of Trade Unions of Uzbekistan.

Enterprises, organizations and institutions in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Labor Protection" and scientific research works in the field of labor protection, targeted programs and other measures aimed at improving and protecting the working conditions of employees has the right to establish a labor protection fund for the purpose of financing activities.

Fund funds strictly:

- to develop programs to improve and protect working conditions in the organization;
- to equip workplaces in accordance with the requirements of labor protection and technical safety rules and norms;
- to carry out scientific-research works in the field of labor protection;
- to improve working conditions and to create safe and effective working conditions, to train employees on labor protection (increase their skills);
- to prevent accidents in production;
- to prevent occupational diseases;
- to provide labor protection services with regulatory legal documents and means of promoting labor protection;
- to hold conferences, seminars, meetings and exhibitions on labor protection;
- to organize international cooperation on labor protection issues;
- to improve working conditions and encourage activities on labor protection;
- used to finance activities aimed at the implementation of measures in other areas of labor protection determined by the internal normative documents of the organization.

Labor protection measures and the amount of funds necessary for financing these measures are stipulated in the collective agreement, if such an agreement has not been concluded - in the agreement concluded between the employer and the trade union committee or other representative body of employees.

When developing prospective and annual plans of the organization's labor protection measures, first of all, dust, pollution with toxic gases, vibration, noise, other dangerous and

harmful production factors, fire-explosion risk, heavy hand productions, sites, objects, technological processes that require reduction (elimination) of labor are determined, as well as reduction of the number of workers (especially women) engaged in harmful productions and heavy work, creation of safer working conditions measures are intended.

Labor protection measures:

current repair of ventilation devices, sanitary-household devices;

fencing the workplace near the buildings, constructions, assembly areas, trenches, ladders, etc. under construction;

preparing, assembling, and disassembling the reservoirs, installing reservoirs, fixing trenches and trenches;

buying, storing, repairing, washing, dusting, drying, disinfecting special clothes and special shoes;

purchasing and testing personal protective equipment and load-holding devices;

provision of workers with treatment-prophylactic food, milk, soap, purchase of sanitary-household and service rooms and provision of services by them;

painting of walls, ceilings, structures, equipment as one of the elements of maintenance of buildings, structures and equipment;

beautification of the territory of the organization, paving of branch roads, sidewalks, landscaping of the territory;

measures to reduce air and water pollution or eliminate pollution, the main goal of which is to create normal sanitary conditions for residential districts located near the enterprise, are not included.

CONCLUSION. Labor protection measures should be provided with funding sources and material resources.

The funds of the fund are spent within the budget approved by the relevant management body of the organization based on the information of the labor protection service.

Control over the use of the funds of the fund is carried out by the chief accountant and the trade union committee or another representative body of the employees, along with the employees of the labor protection service.

Unused funds of the fund in the reporting year are not withdrawn, they are carried over to the next year and are used for the purposes specified in this Regulation and internal regulatory documents of the organization.

Funds allocated for the financing of labor protection measures cannot be used for other

purposes, including for the repayment of arrears on taxes and compulsory payments, other creditor indebtedness.

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